

DIVERSITY AND UNITY

MORPHOLOGY OF ARCHITECTS AND ENGINEERS

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ABSTRACT

The new demands for a more sustainable built environment, as well as the need for a comfortable and healthier indoor environment, lead to a more complex design process. This has consequences for the role of the different designers involved in the building design process. Their different expertise must be used more effectively to reach together better solutions. In this research the effect of using morphological overviews was investigated, as well as the relation of morphological overview as a kind of mental model of the design team. The effect of application of morphological overviews was positive on the overall team performance. However the results were different for architects, they evaluated the appropriateness positive but still it was found that there was decrease in the number of functions and solutions generated by them. Unifying different disciplines is complex given the diversity of the building design team members. More research is necessary to determine if it could prove to be useful to use of morphological chart in combination with a mental model of the design team.

Keywords: Integral design, morphology, building design.

INTRODUCTION

To study the diversity and unity of architects and engineers it is good to start with two quotes and to look at the origin of the words architect and engineer to illustrate the diversity between them and to show as well the unity.

Santiago Calatrava gave an excellent characteristic of the architect in his AIA Gold Medal Acceptance Speech: *“When I do not know the future of our profession. But we know our past, to which we must be responsible. Our past tells us that we are human beings—fallible and limited—who do technical work with material*

things. Our past also tells us that somehow, through an agency we do not understand, we can sometimes create art. When that happens, we are no longer merely workers. We became “ARCHITEKTON” - the first among workers.” Calatrava (2005) explains in his speech that the word Architecture goes all the way back to ancient Greece, the beginning of the word, “ARCH” means “the first.” To be an architect, to the Greeks, was to have the responsibility that comes with priority. The second part of the word is “TEKTON” meaning “a worker” and is closely related to “TEKNIKI” - the word that the Greeks used for a technique which in turn, is very close to the Greek word “TECHNI” also use for “art”. So for the Greeks, the practical, mechanical skill of a worker could give rise to art. When you saw the result of technique and it moved you, then it became art. About the engineer Stan Ackermans gave a description in *The Engineer*(1986): *“They are integrators, people that can oversee, make connections and yet know exactly how every component functions. Engineers also have to know how we get knowledge and ideas.”* The word *Engineer* (Oxford dictionaries (2011) comes from the Old French *engineer* which comes from medieval Latin *ingeniator*, from *ingeniare* 'contrive, devise' which comes from Latin *ingenium*.

To conclude the architect is traditionally more focused on design were as the engineer is more focused on knowledge. In architecture it was not so long ago that designers tended to view knowledge with disdain, as a hindrance to unfettered creativity (Heylighen et al 2009), but that is changing now. The architect in his quest to create art and the engineer in his pursuit to use knowledge and ideas in a capable way, they need each other to reach a level of technique which becomes art. Was in the past the focus on the creation of ideas now more and more

the focus is on creation of knowledge as nowadays there a need for sustainable architecture. During the last decades, the main focus of research in Building Design was on reduction of energy consumption of buildings. The strong focus on the energy reduction led to situations in which health and comfort are endangered. Presently application of sustainable energy systems and components is too complex for integration in the early stages of building design. As a result, sustainable design options are added to the final stages of the design. This results in sub-optimal designs and rejection of the proposals. There is a mixed performance in the realization of sustainability objectives, there are a number of key barriers hindering progress and as a result the process became more complex (Williams and Diar 2007). Sustainability is a real-world problem which cannot be solved by any one discipline alone (Dykes et al 2009). It requires multiple disciplines with a shared theoretical understanding and an agreed interpretation of knowledge according to Gibbons et al. 1994 (Dykes et al 2009). This knowledge is the starting point of creative collaborations that cross disciplinary boundaries and is essential to innovation. This can lead to the occurrence of boundary spanning, where ideas from one domain, discipline or functional area are important into another (Joyce et al 2010), in a way that solves new problems or presents new solutions (Burt 2004, Rosenkopf & Nerkar 2001).

CHANGING ROLE OF THE DIFFERENT DESIGNERS/CONSULTANTS

In building design the role are changing of architects and traditional discipline based consultants. The need is felt to integrate the different disciplines based views to an integral approach. Building physics consultants have to do more than just building physics as stated by one of the major Dutch building consultants firms. Every possible attention in building physics is paid to a healthy, safe and pleasant living. And so to give form and direction to the factors which influence the living and working environment, such as light, air, noise, temperature and draughts. This in relation to aspects such as energy and sustainability (DGMR 2011). Building physics should no longer be limited to determining how thick an insulating layer must be or

checking the rate of condensation. Building physics must focus on people's health and comfort, as well as sustainability. A satisfactory ambient climate in a sustainable way is the new building physics consultants' starting point.

Some building physics consultants want to be the new key player within the team, the director of the design orchestra. In the capacity of consultant, they want to be the link between designers and building services engineers, in that they provide solutions in which technology is integrated with the building as far as possible (DGMR 2011). By combining structural and building-services related solutions, they want to make significant improvements in the areas of ambient climate and energy consumption. In the capacity as building consultants they want to draw up the pre-conditions to which the building-services consultant and architect, for example, must adhere in their designs (DGMR 2011).

However the only right solution for improving the overall quality of building design can be found within the design team itself and letting the design team functioning as a real team. This means for each member within the design team equal respect for the role of each team member, though still with its own discipline based expertise. All disciplines so also building physics have points of convergence with many other disciplines.

The exchange of knowledge within the development team, but also between various fields of expertise, is indispensable in reaching a high-quality solution (DGMR 2011). This exchange between designers from different disciplines leads to a situation in which each individual is able to come up with ideas for the best conceivable living environment, the most perfect sustainable and an optimal energy-efficient construction. All conceivable options should be considered in this process, so that not a single possibility is overlooked.

Building design is changing (Holzer 2009) and so should architects change their traditional role in the design process (Kang et al 2010). The design process for a future building is quite differently framed from a standard code compliant building and it is essential that an Integrated Design Process is used from the outset of the project to ensure success (American Institute of Architects 2009). A cost-effective Building design is a realistic possibility with an

integrated design process (Torcellini et al 2010). In building design there is a real necessity for a paradigm shift. Traditionally the building concept is solely designed by the architects, only after the first analysis the other disciplines get involved and concept generation. However due to increasing complexity it is not possible for the architect to solve all the problems on its own. Therefore there is a change to design teams in the early stage of conceptual building design, which bring together designers from different disciplines, the so called Integrated design approach. These disciplines are besides architecture, structural engineering, building technology, building physics and building services. However from earlier research it was concluded that it is not enough to just put the different designers (architects and engineers), together right from the start of a project. As in such a design team there is a lot diversity based on the different discipline backgrounds of the participants which causes problems. To investigate these problems and to try to find solutions for them, since year 2001 'integral approach' has been propagated within Dutch building design practice Zeiler et al 2005). The Technische Universiteit Eindhoven (TU/e) continuously develops 'learning by doing' workshops, this in cooperation with the Royal Institute of Dutch Architects (BNA), the Dutch society of consulting engineers (NLIingenieurs) and the Dutch society for Building Service engineers (TVVL). The workshops are used to test a specific adapted design method to structure the design process and to stimulate proactive design actions from different design team members.

METHODOLOGY

INTEGRAL DESIGN

The frame for structuring actions of team members is found in 'Integral Design' model, a collection of design tools within a design process matrix. Integral Design is problem oriented and distinguishes, based on functional hierarchy, various abstractions and/or complexity levels during different stages and design activities (Zeiler and Savanovci 2009).

During all workshops, following the assignment presentation the design process was observed and no further intervention took place. Observations were conducted in two different ways: (1) noting design

teams' activities using observation forms (by students) and the last two series the workshop sessions were registered by video cameras because the participants found the student something disturbing their concentration, (2) by taking photographs of design team's work (by researchers, in 10min intervals), (3) the acquired data was analysed together with the material produced by the design teams. The additional resources of information were the questionnaires that participants had to complete after each day session and another questionnaire after a period of approximately six months.

Over the past four years 5 series of workshops have been conducted, these typically include around twenty participants and lasted for two or three days. A total of 107 designers participated in the five workshop series, in which 74% of the designers were present during all days. The average age of the participants, all members of either BNA or ONRI was 42 and they had on average 12 years of professional experience. Step by step improvements were made to the concept of the workshops based on the responds and evaluations by the participants. In total 5 series of workshops were organized based on earlier experiments (Zeiler et al 2005). After each workshop the set-up and the results were evaluated and adjustments made. The experiences of the first three workshops 'learning by doing' series led to a final setup used the final workshops series 4 and 5, see Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Final workshops series (Savanovic 2009)

Essential element of the workshop were besides some introduction lectures the design cases on which the teams of designers had to work and which they

had to present at the end of each session to the whole group. In the current configuration (Fig. 1) stepwise changes to the traditional building design process type, in which the architect starts the process and the other designers join in later in the process, are introduced in the set up of the design sessions. The first two design sessions on day 1, provide reference values for the effectiveness of the involvement of all designers from different disciplines right from the start. On the 2nd day the morphological overviews introduced. The application of morphological overviews during the set up of the third design session enabled transparent structuring of design functions/aspects and the generated (sub) solution proposals. Additionally, the third setting provided the possibility of one full learning cycle regarding the use of morphological overviews. After the feedback about their use of morphological charts and the morphological overview all teams had the basic knowledge to apply them correctly.

MENTAL MODELS

Researchers in several disciplines have applied the construct of mental models to understand how people perform tasks based on their knowledge, experience and expectation (Badke-Schaub et al 2007). Most research on team mental models focused on operating complex technical systems (Mohammed et al 2010) which activities mostly follow standard operations and procedures rather than design which involves inventive problem-solving. Shared mental models of creative tasks are dependent on the task demands for every domain (Neuman et al 2006) and need therefore different types of models to describe teamwork processes. Starting from the four models that are commonly used by Cannon-Bowers (the task model, the equipment model, the team model and the team interaction model) Badke-Schaub proposed a modified framework for design activities (Neuman et al 2006), see Table 1.

Table 1. Types of mental models in design (Neuman et al 2006)

Types	Knowledge content about
Task	the task, including task procedures, product knowledge and tools
Process	Problem solving strategies, idea generation and evaluation
Team	team-mates understanding, roles, interactions and communication channels
Competence	confidence and beliefs in one's own and the other members' strengths and capabilities

Team Mental Models are not meant to only refer to multiple levels or sets of shared knowledge but also to a synergetic functional aggregation of the teams mental functioning representing similarity, overlap and complementarity (Langan-Fox et al 2004). Therefore using mental model research to investigate design processes might help to understand how the solution finding creativity part evolves and how it is communicated in a team (Badke-Schaub et al 2007). Designing typically takes part in an organizational context, with relations to clients and users and specific market situation. Thus, an analysis of mental models in design teams needs to include context knowledge that reflects the given situation, see Fig. 2. (Badke-Schaub et al 2007).

Fig. 2. Mental models (Badke-Schaub et al 2007)

By applying the integral design method the design team's process can be described by the morphological charts and the morphological overview as a mental model of the design team. So, it is not surprising that design thinking - the cognitive processes that are manifested in design action - has become recognized as a key item of research for understanding the development of design practice and design education. In the past simplifying paradigms have been attempted- such as viewing design simply as problem-solving, or information-processing, or decision-making, or pattern-recognition - and all have failed to capture the full complexity of design thinking (Cross 1991). Designers specifically know the "artificial world", the human-made world of artifacts. Designers know how to propose additions to and changes to the artificial world. Their thinking, knowledge, skills, and values lie in the techniques of the artificial (Cross 2001). Prescriptive methods for structuring design processes

based on the existing theories of design still predict designer's actions only on an overly abstract level. This a model for design thinking is based on a simplified model by de Vries (1994). Consider an individual designer working on a design problem here two worlds can be distinguished connected to the activities taking place. One world consists of the design object, the object description and the design knowledge all part of the real world: the knowledge world K, while there is also a hidden undefined conceptual world in the mind of the designer, see Fig. 3.

Figure 3. Designer and World view (de Vries, 1994)

Essential are different roles of a designer, he is descriptor of the design object and as soon as he has sketched or described the design object he becomes also an observer within his own design process. When we look at a representation of a design team, we can more easily see the different roles, because when one designer is active as descriptor the other automatically become observers till they become active and the roles are changed, see Fig.4. This figure shows the dualistic role pattern of a designer. Sometimes he descriptor of his own activated mental design process. While on other moments in the design process he observes the activities of the other design team members. This rather simple model provides us a basis to look into design process. To test our approach of the morphological charts/overview they were applied in arranged workshops as part of a training program for professionals. Essential we were interested in the use of morphological chart and morphological overviews as a way to represent the activation of the

design task. The theoretical pre-assumption model is represented in Fig. 5.

Figure 4. Interaction model of designing within a team with changing role of the designer as descriptor or observer

Figure 5. Interaction model within a team with the designer as descriptor/observer

Based on the current situation, each design team member architect, structural engineer, building physics consultant and building services engineer perceives reality due to his/her active perception, memory, prior knowledge and needs, see Fig. 6. It shows that the morphological charts and morphological overview of the Integral Design method can make transparent some parts of the team mental model. Compared to the team mental model by Badke-Schaub the distinction between the conscious and subconscious is more emphasised as well the use of morphological charts and morphological to illustrate of each individual designer to the team's design process. This can be seen as a first step to make the team's mental model more visible and transparent to other stakeholders involved in the design process.

Figure 6. Design Team mental model in analogy with the model by Badke-Schaub et al. 2007

RESULTS

Different set up for the workshops were tested but for the series 4 and 5 the final form of the workshops described herefore was used. All teams worked on the same design tasks to be able to compare the outcomes of the design process from the different settings (Savanovic 2009). Here the results of the final workshop are given. Fig. 7 shows the average number of aspects and sub solutions generated by all the teams in the two different settings 1 and 4, this clearly shows that, as expected, more aspects/functions were discussed and sub solutions were generated in setting 4 compared to setting 1. When comparing the overall results of sessions 1, 2 and 4 the difference between the different interventions can be seen, see Fig. 7, between session 1 and 2 the effect of starting working together from the first moment in the process and between session 1 and 4 the effect of working

together from the first moment in the process but then with a supportive design tool.

Figure 7. Comparison of the number of functions and sub solutions design sessions 1, 2 & 4 of the final workshops series

DIFFERENCES BETWEEN DISCIPLINES

From the analysis of the workshops it could be concluded that, the number of functions and aspects

considered, as well as the number of subsolutions offered, was significantly increased by applying the Integral design method with its use of Morphological Overview. A good example of this increase can be seen from the results from session 1 (without morphological charts and morphological overview) compared with the results of session 4 (with use of morphological charts and morphological overview), see Fig. 8.

Figure 8. Average number of functions proposed by a discipline during session 1 and 4 of the 4th workshops series

The effect of the design intervention is different for each discipline par example there is a decrease of outcome for architects and building physics consultants but an increase of outcome by building services, structural engineers and for the design

Figure 9. Average number of sub solutions proposed by a discipline during session 1 and 4 of the 4th workshops series

DISCUSSION

Direct at the end of the workshop the participants were asked to fill in a questionnaire in which

questions were asked about the importance of the use of morphological overviews within the design process. The results of the questionnaires improved through each version (Savanović 2009). By evaluating the average results of 5th workshops with that of the overall average of all workshops it is concluded that the final concept was indeed an improvement on all aspects compared to that of the earlier concepts, see Table 2.

Table 2. Overview results questionnaires participants workshop series.

	series 5	Total all series
Number participants	18	107
Percentage returned questionnaires	97%	94%
	(% yes)	(% yes)
MO increases relevant alternatives	79	70
MO improves insight in other disciplines	85	73
MO relevant for own discipline	80	74
MO helpful for communication	81	73
MO positive effect design process	77	69
MO positive effect final design	75	64
Workshop fit for professional education	89	83

The 5th workshop setting proved to be the right one. The overall ratings were never before as high, although there are no extremes and there for a continuous improvement during the workshops series. Participants of the five series workshops were approached six months after their workshop participation in order to get their ‘second opinion’ on the proposed approach and to assess the effects that the Integral Design method has had on their practices. Only the reactions from designers who participated during all design sessions of a series were taken into account. The results of the most relevant questions related to the integral design method and morphological overviews are given below in table 2.

Table 3. Ratings by participants’ workshops series 1 to 4 after a working period of six month’s

	architects	BPC’s	BSC’s	SE’s	Total
Number participants	24	22	19	8	73
Percentage returned questionnaires	67%	68%	58%	63%	66%
Used morphological overviews in the last six months? (% yes)	49	35	32	60	41
Use morphological overviews relevant own discipline? (% yes)	63	60	65	84	65

Comparing the results of the questionnaires direct at the end of the workshop and after a period of 6 month's there is only one remarkable difference in rating, the use or expected use of morphological overviews, 6,5 compared to 4,1, see Fig. 10. When asked if they think the workshop approach is suited for the permanent educational program the participants are after the period of 6 month's even a bit more positive as compared to direct after the workshops; 8,5 compared to 8,3. This indicates, in contrast to the low application of the Integral Design method by the professionals in practice, the added value of the approach to the practice of building design to the professionals.

Figure 10. Comparison evaluation results directly after and after six month's of the workshops

Remarkable is the almost same difference between expected use and real use of morphological overviews of all the different disciplines of almost 25%, see Fig. 11. Still on average 40% of the participants used morphological overviews in their practice. What we can see is the relative low score for building physics consultants and building services consultants. They both normally come in a later phase of the design process often after the conceptual design phase. This meant that they could not introduce the morphological overview anymore. Also most of the participants were working in large ongoing projects which already were past the conceptual design phase. That might be the explanation of the low score.

BPC = Building Physics Consultants
 BSC = Building Services Consultants
 SE = Structural Engineering consultants

Figure 11. Results questionnaires on different aspects of the use of MO's of workshops series 1 to 5 after a working period of six month's

From the analysis of the workshops it could be concluded that, the number of functions and aspects considered, as well as the number of subsolutions offered, was significantly increased by applying the Morphological Overview. A good example of this increase can be seen from the results from session 1 (without morphological charts and morphological overview) compared with the results of session 4 (with use of morphological charts and morphological overview), see Fig. 7.

The comparison of design setting 1 and 2 presents the effect of introducing all the different designers from the start without using support. This led to a decrease of the number of aspects and subsolutions, indicating a less effective design process. This is inline with literature about brainstorm experiments (Nijstad et al 2003), were they also found out that by just bringing together more designers the productivity doesnot increase compared with the results from individual sessions. The team has to have a kind of guidance, in our case the Integral design method.

The activation of design team member's knowledge through a priming manipulation such as the use of morphological charts of morphological overviews leads to the generation of possibly generation of more (original) solutions. However there is a uncertain relation between quantity and quality. The most parsimonious interpretation of the quantity-quality relation is chance (Rietzschel et al

2007): each generated idea has an equal probability of being a good idea. Therefore, according to the laws of chance, the number of good ideas produced should increase in dependency of the total number of ideas produced (Rietzschel et al. 2007). Still there is no simple linear relation between total productivity and the number of good ideas.

All teams used the morphological charts to produce their morphological overview and 3 out of 4 teams even used their morphological overview to present their final design. More important is that there is a possibility to look into more detail into the design process (Zeiler and Savanovic 2009). It was found that groups had a different outcome of the process. In some of the groups the architect remained dominant and no extension of the design space took place, no functions were added when the step was made to get from the individual morphological charts to the design team's morphological overview (Zeiler and Savanovic 2009), see Fig. 12. Sometimes the team started working from only one function and extended with new functions, while in other cases there was a balanced input from the morphological charts into the morphological overview by all

disciplines. Besides the functions also the process of the generated sub solutions by the design teams can be traced and illustrated with the help of the morphological charts and morphological overview, see Fig. 13. This makes it possible to analyze the input from each designer to the final solution process. What also can be seen is that the teams add functions and sub solutions into the morphological overview that were not part of any of the morphological charts. Through the discussion forming the morphological overview new insights occur and as a result new functions. Also new sub solutions are thought of and put into the morphological overview. Using the morphological charts and morphological overview it is now possible to illustrate the connections by lines, see Fig.13. The boxes with thicker black lines around them represent functions or sub solutions which were not mentioned in any of the morphological charts and have therefore no connecting lines connected to them. As can be seen not all functions and sub solutions of the morphological charts find their way into the morphological overview. After discussion the team focused on the most relevant items.

Figure 12. An example of the transformation of functions of individual Morphological Charts into a Morphological Overview of the design team

Figure 13. Example of transformation of the design team's individual morphological charts into the teams' Morphological Overview

CONCLUSIONS

The diversity of disciplines, especially between architects and engineers, involved in building design makes it difficult to reach unity and true synergy within design teams necessary to solve the new more complex design tasks. To support the design process a design tool was developed morphological overview. The use of morphological overviews has a positive effect of the building design team performance. However the effect of the application of morphological overviews is different to architects compared to the effect on engineers. It is necessary to study these differences in more detail. For this the application of the mental model proposed by Badke-Schaub in combination with the application of morphological chart of each individual designer could be useful, see Fig. 14.

Figure 14. Mental model by Badke-Schaub and the use of morphological charts and morphological overview

The transformation from morphological charts to the morphological overview gives an impulse to the

active perception and stimulates the memory. The design team's participants come up with additional sub solutions that were not notated in the individual morphological chart. Also some new functions were generated and related sub solution concepts. Although at this moment in the research it is not possible to tell whether they are really new or were part of the already existing knowledge of one of the participants, this might be the process leading to new concepts.

Almost in none of the design processes the architect is the dominant 'input factor' for the design process. Applying the described design method leads to a more balanced input from all disciplines involved. As a result engineers become more pro-active involved instead of their traditionally more reactive role.

What was found out analyzing the transformation of individual morphological charts into the morphological overview, is that engineers are more capable of defining functions and make a better distinction between functions and sub solutions. Architects more often confuse function and connected sub solution, they are not used to think and act in a more strict logic structure. Still this diversity is important as from the different styles and perspectives new insights occur which are important to come up with the necessary new solutions.

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